

Methods of Developing Critical Thinking in Leaders of Educational Institutions as a Social-Pedagogical Problem

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Abstract:

In this article, the socio-pedagogical problem of critical thinking, ways of developing critical thinking in the heads of educational institutions, and directions of the socio-pedagogical problem are highlighted.

Keywords: critical thinking, methods of developing critical thinking in educational institution leaders, socio-pedagogical problem, socio-pedagogical problem directions.

Today, the socio-economic changes taking place in various spheres of society in our country determine the reform of the labor market, the heads of educational institutions touch on a wide range of socio-professional issues related to solving the problems of adaptation to modern professional conditions. . Today, graduates of higher educational institutions are required to have new professional thinking, high mobility, competence, and tolerance.

These requirements are primarily related to the need to form and develop critical thinking, which is an integral part of the professional competence of the heads of educational institutions. Perspectives are opened only for the critical thinking of leaders of educational institutions that are formed at a sufficiently high level. Professional activities that require transformation. Development of leaders of educational institutions as independent, creative and critical individuals with business relations and cooperation skills and abilities. A thinking activity subject, non-standard approaches to solving production problems. Students of the Higher Vocational School should be well prepared for

continuous self-development, innovation, diversity of ways to achieve goals, independent decision-making, collegiality, initiative and flexibility.

However, the analysis of the practical activities of the heads of educational institutions shows that at the beginning of their professional activities, most of them do not know how to implement these qualities in practice and even do not have experience in the implementation of such powers.

Leaders of educational institutions are often not sufficiently prepared for real professional activity, they are weak in motivation for effective cooperation in a team, thinking about mistakes and shortcomings, etc. At the same time, among the leaders of educational institutions, the opinion that the critical thinking of employees is formed automatically during the training process is achieved only as a result of many years of professional activity at the highest level. But practice and research do not confirm a direct connection between the specialist's work experience and the level of critical thinking formation. Therefore, an important task of professional education is to search for technologies, the purposeful and systematic formation of critical thinking of the leaders of educational institutions is already at the stage of professional training.

Leaders who work in educational institutions and rely on traditional approaches to the formation of critical thinking, today they face difficulties in involving employees in the process of developing thinking in various professional and social relationships. In this regard, we can conclude that the process of formation of critical thinking of the heads of educational institutions does not correspond to the processes of educational reform. Both content and form are ways to develop critical thinking. The theoretical analysis of various modern studies shows aspects of formation of critical thinking in philosophical science, social, psychological and pedagogical level.

"Critical thinking" technology activates the intellectual and emotional activity of a specialist and allows him to involve his personality in the work process.[1]

Casserly in 2012 identified critical thinking as one of the ten skills needed for employment in nine of the ten most in-demand jobs [2].

In modern literature, there are many definitions of the phenomenon of critical thinking [3], which are structured within two approaches: philosophical and cognitive-psychological. Philosophical approach traditionally developed from the works of Socrates, Plato, Aristotle, and in the modern tradition - from the works of Matthew Lippmann and Richard Paul. At the center of the philosophical approach is a hypothetical critical thinker with a certain set of characteristics, but no model of behavior or behavior that the critical thinker is capable of performing [4].

The relevance of the problem and the interest of scientists in solving a number of defined problems. Among the scientists studying this problem from a philosophical, psychological and pedagogical point of view are E. de Bono, D. Dewey, R.H. we can mention such researchers as Johnson, D. Clouster, M. Lipman, K. Meridith, D. Spiro, J. Steele, C. Temple, D. Halpern, P. Freire. Only in the last 5-10 years, the task of developing critical thinking of students has attracted the attention of local scientists (V.A. Bolotov, A.V. Butenko, A.V. Korjuev, V.A. Popkov, G.B. Sorina, D.M. Shakirova, L.I. Shragina, etc.) the formation of critical thinking began in the 70s of the last century (M. Veksler, A.S. Bayramov, A.I. Lipkina, U.M. Munchaeva, V.M. Sinelnikov, L.A. Rybak) and was revived only in the late 90s.

Group learning technologies that allow leaders of modern educational institutions to flexibly adapt to the business world and the new management system are based on the manifestation of critical thinking. In this regard, the conditions for the formation of critical thinking in the framework of universal and professional competences based on the application of the heads of educational institutions, different group forms of organizing the work of the heads of educational institutions should be studied.

The problem of the optimal selection of group forms of the organization is in the attention of researchers of various scientific schools, where the educational activity of the heads of educational institutions has always been in the center of attention. However, the issues of relations between the formation of a special type of (critical) thinking in the heads of educational institutions and the collective form of organizing activities in the educational process, which is widely used in management, are not sufficiently developed even today.

People have a great desire for criticism and self-criticism, but the lack of knowledge and skills to apply this knowledge in practice leads to criticism, that is, wrong criticism. Criticism can take the form of a simple quarrel to clarify "Who is right", and as a result of scientific discussions, a common opinion is developed, or each of the opponents disagrees with his opinion. Criticism differs from criticism in logical expression. Critical thinking, of course, is formed by logic. However, the main role of forming critical thinking belongs to teachers. The traditional inattention of university teachers to pedagogy and teaching technology has led to the fact that teachers of higher education.

Similar information V.A. Popkov, A.V. Korjuev, he studied two hundred teachers of pedagogic and medical universities.

Critical thinking does not emerge spontaneously as a by-product of regular training in any field. In order to achieve the expected results, systematic actions, actions aimed at improving thinking are required.

Each new fact is subject to critical reflection, and the process of knowing becomes stronger and more individual and effective. The formation of critical thinking is a learning process, and as a result, natural personality qualities such as curiosity, sensitivity, self-confidence, independence, politeness, freedom of speech (inhibition), and courage in expressing an opinion are strengthened. The ability to develop creative and critical thinking and teach these types of thinking to students defines the degree. Because this thinking is social, it is most fully manifested in speech, debate, argument, and then solving group problems in public.

There is a revision of the position of in, which becomes more of a "coordinator" than a direct source. Knowledge and information. The traditional "teacher-student" paradigm, i.e. transfer of knowledge and experience taking into account the individual, is not able to establish the internal qualities of the student. As a change in the teacher's professional position, it causes the student to act in the learning process. A "partner" with a certain life experience. Thinking from the perspective of the theory of Synergetics, the learning process can be emphasized, which is associated with a special form of communication between the "coordinator" and the "partner", in which wisdom and lessons from life experiences are learned. It happens.

Leaders of educational institutions working in accordance with critical thinking develop the content of all kinds of pedagogical situations from the point of view of seeing the possibility of making the process of formation critical, making students' thinking more intensive and effective, using methods of forming problem thinking, and using special methods, methods and methods. The practical application of the humanitarian principle to the educational process "requires the introduction of pedagogical technologies based on a personal active approach, critical, creative thinking, problem-solving, decision-making, and the ability to work cooperatively."

Critical thinking is not only formed by itself in the course of life, but also through special pedagogical tools, special training, exercises, and training. We identified the collective form of educational organization as the most effective form of educational organization that contributes to the formation of critical thinking in the heads of educational institutions. Theoretical justification of the effectiveness of choosing a collective form of educational organization can be observed in the works of M.I. Makhmutov, D.M. Shakirova, Y. Skalkova, Evrim Ustunluoglu, G.I. Antonenko and

others.

If we conclude from the above points, in our opinion, the most effective way to develop the critical thinking of the heads of educational institutions is to train them with the help of special courses. Conducting special courses and seminars to increase the level of critical thinking makes it more convenient for him to work on himself at any time during his professional career.

The development of critical thinking in the heads of educational institutions as a socio-pedagogical problem includes a number of important factors. Critical thinking is a necessary skill for leaders not only to improve the educational process, but also to solve complex social, economic and cultural problems. This process is manifested as a socio-pedagogical problem in several directions:

1. The role and responsibility of the leaders of educational institutions: The leaders determine the development strategy of the school or university. It is important that their critical thinking skills, quality of management decisions and innovative approaches serve the benefit of society and students. A lack of critical thinking can lead to traditional, unchanging systems.
2. Social changes and education system: In the current period, rapid changes are required in the education system. Leaders must be ready for social problems, digital transformation, changes in the labor market and other factors. In this process, critical thinking helps leaders analyze the current situation, develop new strategies, and implement advanced educational practices.
3. Methods of developing critical thinking skills: To develop critical thinking in leaders, targeted trainings, advanced training courses and improvement of training programs are required. In this process, leaders are developed by analyzing educational processes, evaluating results, exchanging ideas with colleagues, and using creative approaches.
4. Cultural and social factors: From a socio-pedagogical point of view, critical thinking is related to the accepted norms of the general culture and educational system in society. It is important to create an environment of social support for the formation of independent thinking, critical approach and analytical skills in the leaders of the educational institution.

Thus, the development of critical thinking in the heads of educational institutions is a socio-pedagogical problem, which is a necessary condition for improving the quality of education and being ready for global changes in society.

Of course, the development of the heads of each educational institution is closely related to his interest and demandingness and responsibility for his profession. If every leader sets a goal for himself before starting his professional activity while loving his profession, he will definitely be able to achieve his goal.

References:

1. Шаюсупова А. А., Хайдарова Р. А. Формирование педагогической компетентности преподавателя языкового вуза в системе непрерывного образования //Бюллетень науки и практики. – 2019. – Т. 5. – №. 6.
2. Casserly, M. (December 10,2012)The 10 skills that will get you hired in 2013.Forbes.Retrieved from <http://www.forbes.com/sites/meghancasserly/2012/12/10/the-10-skills-that-will-get-you-a-job-in-2013/>
3. Petress, K. (2004). Critical thinking: An extended definition. *Education*, 124(3), 461-466.
4. Lewis, A., & Smith, D. (1993). Defining higher order thinking. *Theory into Practice*, 32(3), 131–137.